

Nanocrystalline silicon oxide immunosensor for toxicity detection in drinking water

N. Samanta*, C. RoyChaudhuri

Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, Indian Institute of Engineering Science and
Technology, Shibpur, Howrah, West Bengal

Email id: samanta.nir.ind@gmail.com, +919432985373

Abstract:

Drinking water is an essential element for human being. Recently, quality testing of drinking water has become a major issue to the people. It has been observed that, due to the presence of toxic components in drinking water severe health problems have been created. Presently, several researches have been focused on water toxicity monitoring. It has been also observed that, the previously reported processes on water toxicity monitoring cannot detect toxic elements below the pg/l range. In this regard, a monitoring system has been developed with nanoporous silicon impedance biosensor followed by a data analysis with a neuro-fuzzy algorithm to detect toxic substances in water samples. The system has a sinusoidal signal generator with frequency from 125Hz to 52 KHz, sensor drive circuit, RMS to DC conversion unit, controller unit and display unit. This system is capable of detecting aflatoxin B2 and ochratoxin-A properly down to concentration level of 0.1fg/ml.

Keywords: Immunosensor, neuro-fuzzy algorithm, water toxicity monitoring.

References:

1. J. C. Vidal et al., Biosens. Bioelectron. 49 (2013) 146.
2. H. Ghosh et.al., Biosens. Bioelectron. 67(2015) 757.
3. P. Saha et al., IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas. 63 (2014) 2472.
4. V. S. Kodogiannis et al., J. Appl. Soft Comput. 23(2014) 483.